

STUDIES IN INDIAN BAUXITE. PART I. CHROMIUM AND VANADIUM.

BY S. C. GANGULI AND J. DAS-GUPTA.

Cr_2O_3 and V_2O_5 contents of fifteen samples of Indian bauxite have been described in the following paper.

Owing to the importance both from academic and from industrial points of view, bauxite has been the subject of much study. Extensive information on the subject and a very good bibliography will be found in the monograph by Ceril Fox ("Bauxite and Aluminous Laterite", Crossby, Lockwood and Sons, London, 1932).

From time to time, many minor constituents of bauxite from various countries have been reported—Ni, V, Cr etc. in Hungarian bauxite (Gedeon, *Magyar. Chem. Foly.*, 1932, 38, 134); chromium and vanadium in Australian bauxite (Fox, *loc. cit.* p. 143), and so on. So far as the present authors are aware, no investigation on the minor constituents of Indian bauxites have been carried out except by Dr. Bruhl in his analysis of Kala-handi bauxite. The present investigation was undertaken to study the minor constituents of the Indian bauxites and their chromium and vanadium contents are reported in this paper.

EXPERIMENTAL.

In general the method followed for estimation was similar to the one described by Sandell (*Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1936, 8, 336). But two distinct methods were used to obtain *the sum* of the total quantities of oxides.

Method I.—Bauxite (1.5—2 g.) was fused with Na_2CO_3 and KNO_3 and the melt was extracted with water and filtered. The pH value of the filtrate was adjusted to 7.0 with the requisite quantity of H_2SO_4 when all the aluminium was precipitated as hydroxide. After the separation of aluminium, chromium and vanadium were precipitated as mercurous salts, and the precipitate was ignited. The weight of the ignited precipitate gave the value of $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{V}_2\text{O}_5$. The mixed oxides were then fused with Na_2CO_3 , dissolved in water, and chromium and vanadium were estimated in the solution by the colorimetric method (Sandell, *loc. cit.*).

Method II.—The sodium carbonate extract was just neutralised with 4*N*-sulphuric acid and chromium and vanadium were estimated by the colorimetric method of Sandell without the previous separation of alumina.

The results obtained from both the methods agreed within experimental error. Before powdering a sample of bauxite, all extraneous matter which were considered not to be bauxite or highly contaminated bauxite, were excluded by hand picking.

Bauxite No.	Locality.	Method I.		Method II.	
		V ₂ O ₅ .	Cr ₂ O ₃ .	V ₂ O ₅ .	Cr ₂ O ₃ .
134	Netarivat, Palaman, Bihar	0.074%	0.064%	0.078%	0.060%
737	N. E. of Amarkantak. S. Rewah	0.080	0.14	0.0865	0.160
797	Yelurgarh fort, Bombay	0.092	0.125	0.086	0.125
291	Salgipat, N. Lohardaga, Bihar	0.062	0.030	0.067	0.025
790	Radhanagri, Kolhapur, Bombay	0.760	0.062	0.0766	0.060
788A	N. W. of Radhanagri	0.125	0.100	0.119	0.107
978	West of Pipargarh, Balaghat Dist C.P.	0.142	0.055	0.130	0.056
1128	Surganj State	0.058	0.060	0.064	0.056
1142	"	0.115	0.051	0.103	0.051
1559	Yernli Plateau, Bombay	0.089	0.108	0.0914	0.102
4696	Katni, Jabulpore, C.P.	0.067	0.048	0.059	0.054
5038	1 Mile N. W. of Dhagarvadi, Kolhapur, Bombay	0.043	0.056	0.049	0.058
5097	Kapadvaraj. Khaira Dist., Bombay	0.028	0.109	—	—
5098	Jabulpore, C.P.	0.098	0.088	0.108	0.084
5100	Salal, Riasi Tehsil, Kashmir	0.0025	0.013	—	—

From the above data it will be seen that though many samples of bauxite from peninsular India contain appreciable amounts of chromium and vanadium, the sample from Kashmir (No. 5100) contains only a small quantity in comparison with them. No conclusion on the matter is possible without further and more representative examination.

The authors desire to thank the Geological Survey of India for kindly supplying the samples of bauxite and Dr. P. B. Sarkar for suggesting the subject and guidance. Their best thanks are also due to Prof. N. N. Sen for affording all possible laboratory facilities and for his kind interest.

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
B. E. COLLEGE, HOWRAH
AND
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF
SCIENCE, CALCUTTA.

Received March 12, 1938.